

Influence of Area of Land Excavated for Artisanal Gold Mining on Water Access

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ABSTRACT: Artisanal gold mining has expanded rapidly across many river basins globally with significant implications for water resources and local livelihoods. Regardless of modern methods of mining, the sinking of mine shafts or open pits and the excavation of ores and overburden (waste rocks) inevitably disrupt the existing hydrological pathways that in turn affect the surface waters that are connected hydraulically with the disrupted ground water. This study interrogated the influence of the area of land excavated for artisanal gold mining on household water access in the River Yala middle basin. Using a cross sectional research design, spatial measurements of excavated land were quantified and analysed alongside household level data on distance and time taken to access water. Regression analysis was employed to determine the strength and significance of the relationship between the area of land excavated for artisanal gold mining and water access. The findings demonstrated a strong statistically significant relationship between the area of land excavated for AGM and water access that; the area of land excavated for AGM accounted for 64% ($r^2 = 0.64, p < 0.05$) of variation in distance taken to access water and 68%, ($r^2 = 0.68, p < 0.05$) of variation in time taken to access water. This results showed that in River Yala middle basin, AGM land excavations and mounds of rocks have led to: demolition of underground water pipes, covered existing springs, disrupted local underground hydrological stream flow and changes in the paths to water access making households to cover longer distances and time to access. The findings therefore reinforce on the need for strengthening of land use regulation in artisanal gold mining areas and integrated water resource management strategies to safeguard community water access in artisanal gold mining areas.

KEYWORDS: Area of land excavated for Artisanal gold mining; Time taken to Access water; Distance taken to Access Water; Water security; Water Access; Domestic water use

INTRODUCTION

Higher sediment concentrations increase the turbidity of natural waters, (Ripley, 1996). Erosion from waste rock piles or runoff after heavy rainfall often increases the sediment load of nearby bodies; in addition sediment elevation in streams may modify stream morphology by disrupting a channel, diverting stream flows and changing the slope or bank stability of a stream channel. (Johnson, 1997 a: 149). He further connotes that; these disturbances can significantly change the characteristics of stream sediments, reducing water quality. In addition, increased sediment loads and higher sediment loads can also decrease the depth of streams, resulting in greater risk of flooding during times of high stream flow (Mason., 1997). Human land use clearly can generate hydrological and geomorphic responses in the form of increased run off, soil erosion and sedimentation that can have substantial effects on fluvial systems (Allan and Scott ., 2013). Most studies have focused on hydro geomorphic changes caused by land use (Johnson., 1997) the; impact of urbanization Allan and Scott (2013); Impact of climate change (Ncube ., 2021) and impact of water transfer (Ncube., 2019 and Becker., 2022) on river ecosystems. Nonetheless studies are fairly understood on how hydro geomorphic changes initiated by AGM land excavation are impacting on river ecosystem services prompting the current study to focus on the influence of area of land excavated in AGM on water access

Mineral development disturbs soil and rock in the course of construction and maintaining roads, open pits and waste impoundments. Erosion of the exposed earth may carry substantial amounts of sediments into streams, rivers and lakes (Allan and Scott. , 2013). Excessive sediment can clog riverbeds and smother watershed vegetation, wildlife habitat and aquatic organisms (Allan and Scott , 2013). According to Macdonald *et al* (2014) model, land excavation lead to soil erosion and some cases of acid mine drainage (AMD).These processes increase transport of sediments and metals including sulphites and nitrates which are environmental stressors impacting on aquatic ecosystem through changes in habitat quality and quantity. Increased elevated concentrations of metals may result in poor sediments and water quality which in turn can decrease or increase food for and reduce survival of aquatic biota resulting in changes in Macro invertebrates and microbial community, structures and bio- toxicity (Karunia. , 2016). These studies have successfully linked AGM land excavations to reduction in water quality, habitat quantity and changes in microbial

community structures with paucity of peer reviewed literature on the influence of AGM land excavation on water access. This therefore prompted the need for this study to introduce a new study parameter and link AGM land excavation to water access. . Elevated turbidity in natural water, even when they are not necessarily toxic, can have deleterious effects on riverine biota (Henley *et al.*, 2010). They can degrade habitat integrity that often results in reduced biodiversity impeding on fish provision by river ecosystems. (Arthington *et al.*, 2010 and Akrasi. 2011). Also many local citizens often collect water directly from the rivers for domestic purposes including for drinking (Schaifer *et al.* , 2009 and Rossiter *et al.* , 2010).For water treatment companies turbid water and elevated suspended solids also increase water processing costs (Bilotta *et al.*, 2008 and Rossiter *et al.* , 2010). When water is collected at the source, citizens rarely use proper water treatment including removal of sediment particles from the turbid water (Karunia , 2016). Despite these novel insights on increase in water treatment costs, degraded habitat integrity, point source collection of water assertions, scientific literature has done little to bring to the fore how the area of excavated land under AGM is influencing water access at a regional scale.

Mining methods entail ; the sinking of mine shafts or open pits and the excavation of ores and overburden (waste rocks) which inevitably disrupt the existing hydrological pathways that in turn affect the surface waters that are connected hydraulically with the disrupted ground water (Hilson., 2003). Mining activity also disturbs top soils and produces vast quantities of waste rocks with open cast mining producing more waste rocks than underground mining, Removal of topsails can cause erosion and increases sediment loads in the affected riverine ecosystems (Hilson. , 2004) . Based on a historical review of reported data from the Australian gold mining industry, (Mudd . , 2007 b) reported that waste rock increased substantially since the introduction of open cut mining methods in the late 20th century. He also reported that since 1985 annual waste rock production has exceeded the amount of milled ore and predicted that it may be several times the amount of milled ore now and will continue to increase. Despite these assertions, there is a dearth of peer reviewed literature on the influence of area of land excavated under AGM on sediment load in Africa.

Increased suspended solids, turbidity and sedimentation in surrounding water bodies are among the common impacts of mining (Younger Younger and Wolkersdor 2004). The impact is however more prevalent in AGM impacted rivers (Mol *et al.* , 2004 ; Akabzaa *et al.* , 2009) due to the lack of erosion management and control measures at AGM operations. Hydrological changes in rivers can alter available hydrological habitat for aquatic biota (Blanchete *et al.*, 2013). A range of potential environmental impacts of AGM on rivers has been identified including but not limited to changes in hydrology and water quality as a result of, land excavation in mining areas and processing (Macdonald *et al.*, 2014). Fine sediment from tailings ores, waste rocks often remain uncontained and escape into the rivers particularly during the heavy storms which causes flooding and soil loss (Karunia. , 2016). On tropical rivers, Goix *et al.* , (2019) show the impact of some artisanal and small scale gold mining, the study combined two different models to discriminate Hg in bottom sediments of tropical rivers affected by Artisanal Gold .Mining and the part of liquid Hg used by gold-miners in the anthropogenic Hg sources .Increased turbidity may lead to smothering of aquatic plants, habitats and biota (Mol *et al.*, 2020). This therefore calls for an improvement in sediment control in AGM areas.

Artisanal gold mining is characterized with land excavations and open pits resulting in the loss of aesthetic value of the riverine landscape (Shoko., 2002). Mounds of excavated land in AGM are left behind which are swept to rivers leading to increased suspended solids, turbidity and sedimentation in water bodies impacting on river ecosystem services (Akibzaa *et al.* , 2009). Moyo (2009) asserts that excavated rocks from AGM deposited in rivers are a major threat to domestic and industrial water in the African continent. Mensah *et al.* , (2015) showed that surface water based on the rivers Ankobran and Aseree have turned bare and became turbid respectively because of AGM land excavation activities at Prreastea in Ghana. Elevated turbidity in natural water in AGM mining areas have been alluded to (Akrasi . , 2011 ; Henley *et al.* , 2010 ; Arthington *et al.*, 2010; Akibizaa *et al.* , 2008 ; Bilotta *et al.* , 2008).In Zimbabwe Ncube *et al.* , (2019) connotes that, AGM is characterized by massive stripping of overburden leading to the destruction of the river ecosystems. In Ghana Karuria(2016) insinuates that ,gold mining land excavations also disturbs topsoil and produce vast quantities of waste rocks with open cast mining producing more waste rocks than underground mining which is carried to the river channel causing flooding and smothering of benthic organisms. Orimoloye *et al.*, (2020) alludes that, AGM mining operations through land excavation damages the natural landscape, contaminates water and contributes to the destruction of river ecosystem services. These findings have successfully pointed out the negative influence of land excavation to river ecosystems. There was need for quantifiable evidence on how the area of excavated land under AGM influences sediment load which is essential in the management of flooding in rivers.

In Kenya a study conducted by Ogola *et al.* , (2002) alluded that land degradation is registered in AGM areas as a result of soil erosion. Odumo (2014) posits that the ecosystem (soil) was heavily polluted by heavy metals with mercury contamination in soils, biota sediments and tailings Odhiambo (2010) established that AGM has led to contamination of water bodies. On Winam Gulf, a study by Lalah *et al.* , (2008) explores the mean sediment concentration of exchangeable cations in Winam Gulf that most exchangeable cations in sediments ranged between 2% and 20%. These studies have succeeded in showing that AGM land excavations has resulted in environmental degradation and increased sedimentation on general perspective, without linking specific AGM practices to specific river ecosystem services .The current study will narrow its scope of generalization and focus on specific AGM practices and assess the influence of area of land excavated under AGM on water access.

In the study area, Mwamburi (2003) looked into variations in trace elements in bottom sediments of major rivers of lake Victoria

Basin. Onyari (2007) interrogated the distribution of Chromium, Cadmium, Zinc and Iron in Lake Victoria sediments East Africa. Kiluva (2015) used Satellite imagery mapping to establish the extent of flood in the Lower Basin of the Yala River the findings revealed a change in the flood extent of about 34.2 KM² from 1954 to 2010. These studies correctly had their synergies centred on the Lower River Yala basin. The studies dwelt on flood extent with no clear linkages to factors responsible. Nonetheless the current study was centred on the Yala Middle block, which has received less focus by the scholarly world and interrogated the influence of area of land excavated under AGM on water access.

Mounds of excavated land in AGM are left behind which are swept to rivers leading to increased suspended solids, turbidity and sedimentation in water bodies impacting on water quality (Akibizaa *et al.*, 2009). Moyo (2009) asserts that excavated rocks from AGM deposited in rivers are a major threat to domestic and industrial water in the African continent, increasing water treatment costs to make it safe for human consumption. Mensah *et al.*, (2015) showed that surface water based on the rivers Ankobran and Aseree have turned bare and became turbid respectively because of AGM land excavation activities at Preeastea in Ghana. Also elevated turbidity in natural water in AGM mining areas have been alluded to (Akraasi 2011; Henley *et al* 2010; Arthington *et al.*, 2010; Akibizaa *et al.*, 2008 and Bilotta *et al.*, 2008). In Zimbabwe Ncube (2019) connotes that AGM is characterized by massive stripping of overburden leading to the destruction of the river ecosystems through sedimentation of loads. In Ghana Karuria (2016) insinuates that, gold mining land excavations also disturbs topsoil and produce vast quantities of waste rocks with open cut mining producing more waste rocks than underground mining which is carried to the river channel causing flooding. These findings have successfully pointed out that land excavations in AGM areas have led to reduced water quality, increased water turbidity and flooding. However, there was a need to interrogate on the influence of the area of land excavated for AGM on water access which is determined by water quality, turbidity and flooding to broaden the knowledge of understanding on how the river ecosystems are contributing to human wellbeing.

It is estimated that 60% (3.6 tones) of Kenya's annual gold production originates from the AGM sector. Which supports over 250000 AGM workers and one million households having their survival anchored on AGM practices (Barreto *et al.*, 2018; and Planet Gold., 2021). AGM is mainly carried out in river basins for easy access to water for the gold ore processing (Mulinya, 2020). Poverty levels in rural areas which stand high at 40% above the normal national rate of 36% (KNBS 2020), have pushed for gold resource exploitation with less concern on its aftermath on river ecosystems. According to UNEP (2017) fresh water and terrestrial ecosystems are facing serious accumulative pressures from indiscriminate solid waste disposal from AGM activities.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

River basins are critical components to safe and reliable water access. These resources support household water supply, small scale irrigation, livestock watering and local ecosystems. However, increasing land excavations emanating from AGM has resulted in low water quality and turbidity. Threatening availability and accessibility of these water resources. Mercury and cyanide use for gold ore refining in Kenya has contributed to health risks. In the river Yala Middle basin artisanal gold mining involves land excavations characterized with trenches, open pits and removal of topsoil near riparian zones. Such excavation alters natural drainage patterns and increases sedimentation in the basins streams. Despite this, water access is an integral component that not only focuses on water quality but also physical availability, proximity and usability for domestic and productive purposes. Nonetheless numerous studies have examined the environmental impacts of artisanal gold mining on water quality and availability to plant uses, heavy metal contamination. There is limited empirical evidence linking the area of land excavated to changes in water access for local communities. This therefore created a knowledge gap for water resource management, land use planning and policy formulation. Therefore the purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of the area of land excavated for artisanal gold mining on water access in River Yala middle basin Kenya. By quantifying this relationship the study aimed to provide evidence based insights that can inform sustainable land management, safeguard community water access, and support integrated river basin management.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

Artisanal gold mining is a rapidly expanding land use activity across many tropical and sub tropical regions often occurring in rural areas where communities depend heavily on local surface and ground water resources for domestic, agriculture and livelihood needs. While artisanal gold mining contributes to income for the households, it is also associated with extensive land excavations which alter the landscape and hydrological surface flows. Nonetheless many concerns have focused on environmental and public health implications of AGM. Limited empirical research has quantitatively examined how the area of excavated land for artisanal gold mining influences on water access in affected mining communities. The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between the area of land excavated for artisanal gold mining and water access. By integrating spatial analysis and household data, this study sought to generate evidence based findings on how artisanal gold mining land excavations affected on water access. The study findings intended to inform environmental management policies, land use planning and water resource governance frameworks in regions affected by mining. From a broad perspective, the study will contribute to a deeper understanding of the environmental trade offs associated with artisanal gold mining and provide evidence based recommendations.

to support sustainable livelihoods while safeguarding water access for the vulnerable populations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Survey was carried out on the Sub – basins within River Yala middle basin extending from 0.80N, 34.3°E and 0.5°N, 34°E. This covers three counties namely ; Siaya, Vihiga and Kakamega where AGM practices are prevalent .According to KCDP, (2019) , VCDP, (2019) and SCDP , (2019) reports the three counties have experienced land degradation emanating from AGM .

Research design

The study employed a cross sectional descriptive research design since AGM was already taking place over a wide r area and data was obtained over a short period of time.

Study population, Sampling and data collection

The study employed a cross sectional descriptive research design since AGM was already taking place over a wide r area and data was obtained over a short period of time. The specific sample size depended on the extent of AGM activities within the River Yala middle Basin data availability. The sample population for this study consisted of geographical areas and environmental parameters within the Middle Yala Basin, specifically focusing on Sub-basins affected by artisanal gold mining (AGM) practices. Stratified sampling aided in the generation of a representative division of River Yala Middle basin into four zones guided by ; Upper, Upper Middle, Middle Lower and Lower zones. Area based sample frame was generated guided by; Sub – basins of high significance AGM practices, Sub- basins of Moderate AGM practices and Sub – basins with minimal AGM practices. . Based on the area based sample frame, for equal representation, the study therefore picked four Sub-basins which were studied scientifically; Lidambista, Lunyerere , Khwiselo and Ramula. Purposive sampling was applied in the identification of the five constituencies with 11 wards covered by the four basins of study identified. .Therefore the areas of mining constituted these constituencies; Kakamega South, Vihiga, sabatia, Khwisero and Slaya . The Wards where gold mining in the above stated constituencies is as follows: Kakamega South: Eregi, Iguhu, Vihiga: Central Maragoli and South Maragoli; Sabatia: Lyaduywa , Chavakali , Khwisero; Kisa West and Kisa East .Siaya ; Central Sakwa and Ramula . For equal representation stratified sampling aided in the selection of two wards from each constituency for the study purpose. Therefore according to KCDP, (2019) , VCDP, (2019) and SCDP , (2019) the households engaged in AGM from the ten wards are 1790; Since the study population is less than 10000, Therefore a sample size of 321 households was considered using Fisher's *et al .* , 1984 formulae. Simple random sampling was used to obtain 321 respondents from the 1790 artisanal gold miners from every ward. Every artisanal gold miner from the 10 wards was given a number then the list of numbers was randomized through a computer program Microsoft Office Excel. The 321 numbers were randomly selected based on a computer program proportional to each ward's household population engaged in AGM. Therefore the 321 plots were considered for study. Purposive sampling aided in the identification of key Key informants drawn from the three counties of the study area . They included four; area chiefs, village elders , AGM opinion leaders , directors of environment , officers from NEMA and officers from the Ministry of Petroleum and Mining interviewed Data collection was a fundamental step in understanding the influence of area of land excavated for AGM on water access in River Yala Middle Basin of Vihiga, Kakamega and Siaya Counties, Kenya. Primary data collection methods adopted included ; questionnaire, observation, field measurement, counting, recording, and photography. They collected data on parameters of water access such as ; time taken to access water and distance taken to access water , area of land excavated for AGM. These methods were appropriate for data collection because data was obtained by measuring (area of land excavated for AGM and recording the distance and time taken to access water.

Figure.1: River Yala Middle Basin

Data Analysis and Results Presentation

Data cleaning was carried out by checking on missing values, errors and duplicate values. Variables of the study were converted into consistent units of measurements such as acres and minutes and kilometers.. For descriptive statistics , information on rating the influence of area of excavated land for AGM on water access was summarized using frequencies and percentages Simple linear regression analysis tool assisted in determining the nature of influence of area of land excavated for AGM on water access. The areas of excavated land for AGM in acres were regressed with the distance used to access water and time taken to access water for household use per day to generate the r^2 values. The significance level was $P < 0.05$ at 95 % confidence level. The findings were interpreted in the context of the study objective The influence of area of excavated land for artisanal gold mining on water access, and presented in form of scatter plots, and conclusions drawn based on the analyzed results

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Influence of Area of land Excavated for AGM on Distance taken to access water

The current study envisaged to establish the extent to which the area of land excavated for AGM affected water access for domestic use . Respondents were asked to rate the extent to which they agreed. This was done using a Likert scale rated as; 1 strongly disagree 2 disagree 3 Neutral 4 agree, 5 strongly agree the results are as shown in table below: Table 4.13 below shows the results of the rating of the extent of influence of area of land excavated for AGM on water access for domestic use.

Table 1 : Rating of the extent to which area of land excavated for AGM affected on water access for domestic use and percentages of total respondents using Likert scale

Water access for domestic use	1	2	3	4	5
Drinking purpose	0%	0%	0%	18.7 %	81.3%

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Cooking purpose	0%	0%	5.3%	30.0%	64.8%
Water for livestock use	0%	0%	0%	32.7%	67.3%
Water for gardening	0%	0%	0%	33.3%	66.7%
Water for bathing	0%	0%	0%	5.3%	93.5%
Water for cleaning and sanitation	0%	0%	4.0%	30.0%	66.0%
Water for washing	0%	0%	0%	31.7%	68.5%
	1	2	3	4	5
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree

Respondents were asked to rate the extent to which area of land excavated for AGM affects on water access for drinking purpose the results from table 4.13 indicate that; 81.3% strongly agreed and 18.7 % agreed that area of land excavated for AGM affect on water access for drinking purpose .On the basis of the strength that the majority agreed strongly and minority aged, it implies that in the River Yala middle basin access to drinking water is affected by area of land excavated for AGM. . and this findings are therefore consistent with studies such as Nord Iantt *et al . , 2022*; Haddany *et al . , 2019* which assert that areas known for mining operations are highly prone to soil erosion due to soil disturbances. This in turn increases the magnitude of frequency of flooding in the river ecosystems adjacent (Menchoo 2022); (Hilson 2004). The assertions are backed up by Karuria , (2016) that fine sediments from tailing ores, waste has often remained uncontained and escape into the river particularly during the heavy storms which causes flooding. A participant noted that during flooding it becomes difficult accessing clean water for drinking because stream channels are heavily accumulated by soil mud and rocky particles from AGM land excavations .

The researcher also envisaged to establish if the area of land excavated for AGM affected on water access for cooking purposes . The respondents response rate for water access for cooking was as follows; 64.8 % strongly agreed, 30.0 % agreed and 5.3 %..On the basis of the strength that the majority strongly agreed and the minority agreed it implies that area of land excavated for AGM affects on water for cooking in the River Yala middle basin. AGM is characterized with large volumes of mercury , sediments and cyanide release into rivers (Pakhomova *et al 2023*) . The pollutants thereby reduce water safety for cooking purposes (Planet Gold Kenya , 2022) . Also AGM alters stream morphology and reduces surface water availability for cooking purposes (Tampushi et al 2022) .

The researcher sought to establish if the area of land excavated for AGM affected water access for livestock drinking in the River Yala middle basin. The results as shown in Table 4.13 indicate that 67.3 % of the respondents strongly agreed and 32.7% agreed with the statement that the area of land excavated for AGM affects on water access for livestock drinking . Through observation it was noted that the river banks had been weakened posing dangers to livestock at their usual drinking points. This resonates well with assertions that; land use changes led to land fragmentations and abandoned mine pits limiting on livestock mobility as a result of reduction in of grazing areas thereby curtailing access to water and forage (Onoka *et al . , 2022* ; kimiti *et al . , 2023*) . Also a study carried out in Kenya reported that hydrological developments in the Turkwel Basin are associated with land fragmentations impeding on herds in pastoral communities from accessing water and grazing pastures. (Akall , 2021) . Equally a study focusing on southern parts of Kenya range lands noted that ; fencing and subdivision have caused wildlife and livestock difficulties in accessing water and grazing. pastures (Tyrrell *et al . , 2022*) .

The researcher was also out to establish the rate at which area of land excavated for AGM affected on water access for garden watering in the river yala middle basin. According to the results as shown in Table 4.13 , 66.7 % of the respondents strongly agreed and 33.5 % agreed with the statement that , the area of land excavated for AGM affected on water access for garden watering . This confirms the credibility of the rating that area of land excavated tor AGM effected on water access for garden watering. These findings lend credence to assertions that artisanal gold mining causes widespread land disturbance . Through observation it was noted that underground water pipes were demolished by AGM land excavations leading to the loss of piped water. This intern reduced its availability for home gardening . Soil excavation, and sedimentation of water bodies has been reported to reduce water quality and availability for home gardening Spiegel *et al . , 2018*.Also in South East Asia, sedimentation and water diversion have been reported to affect household water for gardening Lowe *et all . , 2018* . In Ghana Yeboah,2013 asserts that ,land disturbance caused by gold mining has resulted to water users walking long distances to access water for gardening .These findings

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however contrast findings by Keita , 2001 that , in Mali river bed mining creates shallow pools that are temporarily used for gardening ,despite being polluted . In Kenya NEMA 2020 reported that sedimentation of rivers blocks irrigation parts thereby making it difficult for the locals to access water for home gardening.

Respondents were also requested to rate the extent to which they agreed that area of land excavated for AGM affected water access for bathing in the River Yala middle basin. The results in Table 1 indicate that 93.5 % strongly agreed followed by 36.5 % who agreed. On the basis of this strength that the majority strongly agreed and minority agreed , it follows that the area of land excavated for AGM affects on water access for bathing purposes. Through observation it was noted that AGM land excavations interfered with underground water recharge through the pumping of water to the surface to access the mine pits. leading to reduced stream flow and drying of streams in the dry season.

In Canada and Australia , mining companies treat water before releasing it to the environment this puts to control some of the bathing risks on the contrast in much of Latin America and Africa , informal mining has led to water pollution by the effluents from mining Teschner , (2012) .Contaminated water from mining can cause skin irritation , fungal infections and skin related complications when used for bathing (WHO , 2017 ; UNEP , 2012) reported that ;countries in East Africa especially Tanzania and Uganda have critical issues on mercury contamination and sedimentation which makes it difficult to access water for bathing for children and women.

Respondents were asked to rate the extent to which area of land excavated for AGM affected on water access for cleaning and sanitation the results from Table1 indicates that; 66% strongly agreed , 30.0% agreed and 4 % were neutral that area of land excavated for AGM affected on water access for drinking purpose .On the basis of the strength that the majority agreed strongly and minority aged, it implies that in the River Yala middle basin water for cleaning and sanitation is affected by area of land excavated for AGM. A report by AP asserts that in Okapi Wildlife Reserve .DRC ; Gold mine run by Chinese mine is polluting rivers through its mercury emissions which undermine access to clean water for washing and sanitation (AP News. 2024) . The standard news paper (2025) report documented that in Khwisero Sub county , pits for gold mining are dug on river banks contaminating water used for washing , and cleaning . Mercury contamination from AGM harm human brain and also drastically reduces on the levels of water access for basic domestic needs like cleaning (AP News, 2025).

In addition the respondents were also requested to rate the extent to which : ‘ area of land excavated for AGM affected on water access for washing ’ in the River Yala middle basin. The results as shown in Table 1 indicate that 68.15 % of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that the area of land excavated for AGM affects on water access for washing and 31.7 % agreed . On the basis of this strength that the majority strongly agreed and minority agreed , it follows that area of land excavated for AGM affects on water access for washing purposes .The findings are in line with assertions that AGM land excavations increase soil erosion and sedimentation which increase on water turbidity reducing on water quality. Water quality has been greatly linked to reduced washing frequencies and increased skin disease risk, (Dietler *et al* . , 2021;Khan *et al* . , 2022) . However the findings of the study contradicts Ondayo *et al* . , (2023) that large scale gold mining improves water infrastructures alongside formal mining financing water points . For AGM mining hotspots in Kenya , we have legal frame work existing but law enforcement is weak at the grass root level with community voices being poorly underrepresented. (Ondayo , 2023) ..This collaborates Nord Iantt *et al* . , 2027; Haddany *et al* . , 2019 that areas known for mining operations are highly prone to soil erosion due to soil disturbances. This in turn increases the magnitude of frequency of flooding in the river ecosystems adjacent (Menchoo , 2022); A participant noted that during flooding it becomes difficult accessing clean water for drinking because stream channels are heavily accumulated by soil mud and rocky particles from AGM land excavations .

The researcher also evaluated the influence of the area of land excavated for AGM on the distance taken to access water in the River Yala middle basin. The area of land excavated for AGM in acres was regressed against the distance taken to access water in metres by the 321 respondents . Figure 2 shows the results of the regression. The results are indicated by a scatter plot of the simple linear regression to test the relationship and nature of influence between the area of land excavated for AGM on distance taken to access water .

Figure 2 : Scatter plot of simple linear regression results showing the influence of area of land excavated for AGM on Distance taken to access water .

The results indicate that 63.5% of the variation in the distance taken to access water can be explained by the area of land excavated for AGM . On the other side 36.5 % of the variation in distance taken to access water can be explained by other factors not considered by this study. These factors constitute ; population, seasonality of rainfall amounts (Paulos *et al .* , 2025 ; Biwort *et al .* , 2022 ; Mudombi 2021), household income and size (Mekonen and Gerba , 2016) alternative water sources (wells, boreholes), terrain slope (Eichelbenger , 2021) , ownership of water containers, and presence of infrastructure (piped supply) (Annys , 2021) could influence distance taken to access water but are not included in the mode

The regression equation displayed on the plot,;Distance (M)=99.56+40.77x shows that there is a strong positive linear relationship between the area of land excavated for artisanal gold mining (in acres) and the distance (in metres) that households travel to access water. These results indicate that increased artisanal gold mining land excavations are forcing local households to walk longer distances to access water, due to ; destruction and contamination of nearby water sources ,disruption of natural hydrological pathways, siltation and diversion of streams caused by excavation and drying or blockage of shallow water access points This supports the thesis that artisanal mining is negatively affecting ecosystem services, specifically water provisioning services in the Middle Yala Basin. As mining expands, water becomes less accessible, increasing households' vulnerability, long distances burden, and exposure to unsafe alternative water sources .

Globally, studies on artisanal mining and water resources have been explored. studies such as (Nordmann, *et al .* , (2022).; Haddany *et al .* , 2019) which assert that areas known for mining land disturbance operations are highly prone to soil erosion due to soil disturbances. This in turn increases the magnitude of frequency of flooding in the river ecosystems adjacent (Menchoo , 2022); Hilson ,2004). This intern impedes on clean water access by communities. In Ecuador Tarras-Wahlberg *et al .* , (2001) alludes to artisanal gold mining disposing heavy sediment loads to streams thereby disrupting downstream water use. In Ghana and Tanzania, (Hilson, 2006; Kitula, 2006) postulate that artisanal gold mining leads not only to water scarcity but also to contamination of fish , posing health risks to dependent populations In Ecuador Tarras-Wahlberg *et a .* , (2001) alludes to artisanal gold mining disposing heavy sediment loads to streams thereby disrupting downstream water use. Bansah *et al .* , (2016) found that larger mined areas corresponded with decreased water quality and increased distances to uncontaminated water sources.

The current findings are in agreement with these studies but focus more specifically on access rather than quality. The issue of water access is critical because while many studies highlight contamination, this research demonstrates that AGM induced land disturbance can directly limit communities from access to water, regardless of water quality considerations. This insight therefore adds to the broader debate on mining impacts by underscoring the dual threat of both reduced access and declining quality.

However the study findings contradicts studies conducted in Latin America (Veiga, 2006 ; Hylander & Maxson,, 2006) which connote that communities sometimes adapt by constructing wells or small reservoirs to cope with reduced surface water availability. Such coping mechanisms appear either insufficient or absent in the Yala middle basin, which explains the significant constraint on water access found in this study. Also Teschner *et al .* , (2014) found weaker correlations in areas with formalized mining regulation,

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suggesting that the degree of environmental management mediates the relationship between mining extent and water accessibility. Therefore, the R^2 value of 0.63 reflects the unregulated or informal nature of artisanal gold mining in the study area. Through observation it was evident that AGM land excavations had led to increased sediment, rock and soil discharge to the streams causing water to dis-colour. This therefore caused households to trek for more distance to access clean water in the River Yala middle basin.

This finding connects directly to the environmental sustainability and public health literature. As the excavation area expands, soil erosion increases, and water bodies become polluted or obstructed (Asiedu, 2013). This forces local populations to travel greater distances to find clean water, increasing daily labor burdens, particularly on women and children who often fetch water (Hilson, 2017). Thus, the quantitative relationship shows a broader social and ecological consequences of artisanal mining documented across developing regions.

Despite the findings, correlation does not imply causation; although land excavation may lead to longer water access distances, the relationship could also be influenced by spatial settlement patterns or mining site selection bias. Future research should consider multivariate models or geospatial analyses to strengthen causal inference (Field, 2018). However, this will call for the isolation of causal pathways and accounting for contextual factors.

4.4.2 The influence of Area of Excavated Land for AGM on Time taken to access water

The study analysis also evaluated the influence of the area of land excavated for AGM on time taken to access water in the River Yala middle basin. The acreage of land excavated for AGM in acres was regressed against the time taken to access water in minutes by the 321 respondents. Figure 3 shows the results of the regression. The results are indicated by a scatter plot of the simple linear regression to test the relationship and nature of influence between the area of land excavated for AGM and the time taken to access water.

Figure 3 : Scatter plot of simple linear regression results showing the influence of area of land excavated for AGM on Time taken to access water .

Figure 3 : Scatter plot of simple linear regression results showing the influence of area of land excavated for AGM on Time taken to access water.

The results indicate that about 68% of the variation in time taken to access water can be explained by the area of land excavated for artisanal gold mining. On the other side 32% of the variation in time taken to access water can be explained by other factors not considered by this study. These factors constitute ; population growth, agricultural water demand, or climatic variability (UNESCO, 2019). This limitation therefore suggests that, while land excavation is a key factor, time taken to access water in the basin is likely influenced by multiple interacting variables. An increase in rainfall reduces walking time to fetch water while high temperatures increases walking time Paulos (2025; Brewster *et al.*, 2023; Carr 2024). Nonetheless, time taken to fetch water depends on more than just distance covered, it also depends on quality of path trailed, walking speed, mode of travel, and

queuing (Winter *et al.*, 2021). This could suggest that other unmeasured factors such as soil composition, groundwater depth, or excavation technique may also play significant roles (Johnson, 2021). (Field, 2018). Factors like the presence of impermeable layers, equipment efficiency, or seasonal fluctuations might influence the distance taken to access water (Field, 2018). However these factors were not explored by the current study.

The regression equation: $\text{Time (min)} = 15.9 + 5.6 \times$ displayed on the plot reveals a strong positive linear relationship between the area of land excavated for artisanal gold mining (in acres) and the time taken in minutes by households to access water. The findings clearly indicate that increased artisanal gold mining activity is prolonging the time required for households to access water. This was evident through observation that in tRiver Yala middle basin, AGM land excavations had led to ; degraded and polluted water sources, destruction or diversion of natural water paths by mounds of rocks and soils , reliance on distant alternative water points due to contamination , increased burden of accessing water mostly on women and school going children. This confirms that artisanal gold mining is significantly disrupting water provisioning ecosystem services in River Yala middle Basin, as households are spending more time than before to secure clean and safe water. The study findings are therefore in agreement with the study hypothesis that area of land under AGM land excavation influences water access. This is coherent because AGM land excavations alter hydrological flows of streams through constant disruptions of natural water sources, increased sediment deposition in rivers and diversion of water stream channels. The compounded effects reduce water quality and reliability of water available to local residents. The study findings therefore are in agreement with studies conducted globally which assert that AGM is characterized by large volumes of mercury and sediments ,cyanide release into rivers (Pakhomova *et al.* , 2023). The R^2 value is consistent with findings from similar studies in hydrology and environmental engineering. For example, Kumar *et al.* , (2019) reported an R^2 of 0.61 when examining the effect of borehole diameter on groundwater accessibility, indicating that spatial dimensions of excavation often account for a substantial proportion of variance in water access time in Sub Saharan Africa where artisanal mining has been linked to diminished water resources. For example, Dondeyne and Ndunguru , (2014) reported that unregulated gold mining in Mozambique contributed to reduced water flows, while Hilson , (2002) identified severe environmental degradation in Ghana's mining regions that limited community access to water . The pollutants thereby reduce water safety for domestic use (Planet Gold Kenya , 2022). Also AGM alters stream morphology and reduces surface water availability for domestic purposes (Tampushi *et al.* , 2022).

Going by the fact that explanatory power of the model is strong, there is need for much considerations to be given to several limitations ; the linear regression R^2 oversimplifies the complex realities of time taken to access water which often involves dimensions such as water quality, distance, affordability, and seasonal reliability (WHO/UNICEF, 2017). Water samples within mining communities in Siaya , Kakamega and Vihiga counties were shown to be polluted, and local sources were compromised; contamination often forces communities to abandon nearby water points and shift to farther water sources Ondayo , (2023) . Through observation , intensive AGM land excavations resulted in huge mounds of rock debris laid to the surface covering the existing springs which were sources of clean water thereby forcing the household members to take much time trekking to other sources of springs. . The study findings are sistent with much of the literature on water insecurity in Kenya which shows proximity to water sources is a key dimension of water insecurity, and that water access inequalities are shaped heavily by environmental degradation, land use change, and poverty. According to Ondayo , (2024) , households farther from safe water sources experience greater water insecurity, and that factors including land degradation or lack of infrastructure exacerbate access burdens.

Therefore future studies could benefit from multiple variable models and longitudinal data to better capture the complexity of the AGM and time taken to access water nexus .The study findings therefore bring to the fore the need for regulation and sustainability. management and environmental governance since AGM practices that entail land excavations have shown to enormously reduce on water access by increasing on time taken to access water This is achievable through policy implementations such as; The findings have significant implications for water resource management and environmental governance. Since land excavations for AGM has shown to substantially reduce water access, there is an urgent need for regulation and sustainable management of artisanal mining activities. Possible strategies include: establishing buffer zones to protect rivers and water catchments from excavation, enforcing land rehabilitation requirements for mined areas. Promoting alternative livelihoods to reduce dependence on destructive mining practices and Integrating mining regulation into Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM) frameworks . Similar policy recommendations have been advanced in Ghana (Banchirigah, 2006) and Zimbabwe (Dube *et al.*, 2016), where unregulated artisanal mining has compromised both water supply systems and community health. The present study lounds this by providing empirical evidence from Kenya's River Yala middle basin.

The results provide strong evidence that increased land excavation under artisanal gold mining significantly increases time taken to access water in the River Yala middle basin . The study has presented quantitative evidence that greater areas of land excavated for artisanal gold mining are associated with increased time burdens for water access in the middle River Yala basin. There is need for future research to undertake longitudinal, spatially detailed and multiple varied designs a to investigate on AGM and its influence on time taken to access water .For policy, protecting water sources, regulating mining proximity, and investing in alternate proximate water supply options are essential to mitigate the water access burden among affected communities This supports the study's second hypothesis and suggests a need for better regulation of excavation practices to preserve water availability in affected

areas. The findings are consistent with international literature but uniquely highlight the strong quantitative relationship between excavation and time taken to access waters. By doing so, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the environmental consequences of AGM and emphasizes the urgent need for sustainable mining.

When the regression analysis for Figure 4.4 and 4.5 is compared to the findings in Table 4.13 that 81.3 % of respondents said they strongly agree that AGM land excavation effect on water access for domestic use, 64.8 % water for cooking, 67.3 % water for livestock use, 66.7 % water for gardening, 93.5 % water for bathing, 66 % water for washing. Apparently the two findings confirm that the area of land excavated for AGM influence on water access in River Yala middle basin. More over information from the four chiefs revealed that ; AGM land excavation has resulted in sediments contaminated with mercury and cyanide being released into water ways making water unsafe for drinking , cooking and bathing. In River Yala middle basin it was observed that , AGM land excavations had resulted in the release of suspended sediments , rocks and mounds of soil. These pollutants have contributed to the turning of water streams into cloudy or discolored changing the water taste making the water hazardous for humans and livestock. Through observation, the researcher also noted silted streams with water that is brown in colour/ dirty as a result of land excavation. This was evident in streams around these mining sites . Muchitu, Viyalo , Iguhu and Ramula.

It was also observed that digging , sluicing and panning in the River Yala middle basin has disturbed river bank soils making it unstable and vulnerable to collapse . This therefore puts the lives of people and animals at risk while accessing water . Households and livestock are therefore forced to walk for more distance, consuming much time to access safe water points .It was also noted that AGM land excavation use of machinery has resulted in the demolition of underground water pipes making it difficult for operations of water supply industries. This means that households connected to the water supply grid experience water supply interferences leading to high maintenance costs. Through observation it was also noted that underground water pipes were broken by AGM land excavations leading to the loss of pumped waters. This reduce availability for home gardening. The excavated mounds of sand , rocks, and soils has resulted to clogging of water ways and water infrastructure ; pipes , pumps , filtration systems making it difficult for households to access water.

It was also revealed that AGM land excavations have resulted in deposition of soil , rocks and gold slurry into streams which has resulted in reduced stream flow or drying up of smaller watercourses, limiting on water access for the households for drinking , irrigation, and other household use. A participant noted that AGM land excavations in the River Yala middle basin has increased the frequency of flooding . During flooding , it becomes difficult to access clean water for drinking because stream channels are heavily accumulated by soil mud and rocky particles from AGM land excavations .

It was also pointed out that AGM land excavations have interfered with the ground water recharge through its excavations that drill pits underground leading to lower water tables in the surrounding areas reducing on water flow to the springs thereby impeding on water access by the household. It came out clearly that during AGM land excavations mounds of sand, rocks, and soil are piled covering much surface on the ground. This in turn has contributed to changes in the paths to water access making households to cover longer distances to access water for domestic use.

Through observation , it was evident that the mounds of sand , rocks and soil excavated through AGM had covered the existing springs and water access points making it difficult for households to access water .This has resulted to much water burdens to the women and girls for they are the ones commonly tasked with fetching water for domestic use.

CONCLUSION

The findings demonstrated a strong statistically significant relationship between the area of land excavated for AGM and water access that ; the area of land excavated for AGM accounted for 64 % ($r^2 = 0.64$, $p < 0.05$) of variation in distance taken to access water and 68 % ($r^2 = 0.68$, $p < 0.05$) of variation in time taken to access water. These results showed that in the River Yala middle basin, AGM land excavations have led to demolition of laid down water pipes , covered springs , disrupted local hydrological systems flow , increased sedimentation in streams and altered the paths to accessing water. As a result households have been forced to trek for longer distances to access clean water .

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to appreciate all key informants in the three counties constituting; Kakamega , Vihiga and Siaya for providing relevant and instrumental information that helped shape the current study .The household heads were also cooperative and assisted in the provision of the required information as provided for in the questionnaire.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study findings therefore recommends that environmental regulations governing artisanal and small scale gold minning be strengthened and effectively be enforced . This is achievable through the protection of riparian buffer zones and mandatory environmental impact assessments. Promotion of sustainable mining technologies and practices , coupled with environmental education for miners is also crucial to mitigate on further ecological damage. We should also have water quality monitoring and integrated watershed management approaches to safeguard water access and reduce pollution risks. There is need to spearhead

diversification of alternative livelihood opportunities. This will help reduce household's over dependency on AGM thereby mitigating on its harmful mining effects.

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